

A Heuristic Proposal for Graph Isomorphism Problem

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Abstract - In computer science and graph theory, it is a fundamental problem whose solution is still being found. The problem involves determining whether two graphs, let Grp1 and Grp2, are isomorphic or not, meaning they have the same structure or not and by re-labeling the vertices or re-arranging the edges of Grp1 and Grp2, the structure/form can be transformed into each other.

In other words, Grp₁ and Grp₂ are said to be **isomorphic** if, there exists a bijection (**one-to-one and onto correspondence**) function, $\forall Vi \in V1 (1 \leq i \leq |V1|)$ onto $\forall Vj \in V2 (1 \leq j \leq |V2|)$ where, V1 and V2 are the number of vertices of Grp1 and Grp2, respectively. And this phenomenon is called **graph isomorphism**.

There is a solution that, Grp1 and Grp2 (with N number of nodes/vertices) are represented in respective two adjacency matrices, say M1 and M2. Without altering M1, permute all the nodes in M2 and match all the permutation with M1. It needs ${}^N P_N = N!$ computation.

Observe the following figures-

For the first glance, we can easily mistake that the above graph are not similar, where $N = 5$. Think for large $N (>> 100000)$, the solution can't be calculated within polynomial time complexity, order of growth $O(N!)$.

Here, we pursue a heuristic approach which ensuring to reduce the complexity within a polynomial time.

Keywords Graph; Isomorphism; Heuristic; Algorithm; Complexity; Random-Number;

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Graph:

A Graph (Grp) is a data structure that can be defined by a non-empty finite set of vertices (V) and a non-empty finite set of edges (E), denoted as $Grp\langle V,E\rangle$.

Our representation:

'M' is the respective adjacency matrix of the graph Grp.

Graph: G
(Un-weighted)

Nodes	1	2	3	4	5
1	0	1	1	0	1
2	1	0	0	0	1
3	1	0	0	1	0
4	0	0	1	0	0
5	1	1	0	0	0

Adjacency Matrix of G: A

1.2 Isomorphic Graphs:

Suppose, two graphs $Grp1\langle V_1, E_1\rangle$ and $Grp2\langle V_2, E_2\rangle$ are said to be **isomorphic** if, there exists **one-to-one correspondence** $\forall V_i \in V_1 (1 \leq i \leq |V_1|)$ onto $\forall V_j \in V_2 (1 \leq j \leq |V_2|)$. And this phenomenon is called **graph isomorphism**.

1.3 Applications:

In various fields, we can apply its application such as

In chemistry, graph isomorphism is applied to identify the molecular structure between two elements. And thus their properties can be predicted.

Complex networks can be analyzed by representing the networks as a graph where, we can identify communities, clusters and other such patterns.

The behavior of various software (basically the malicious, dangerous) is represented in graph and later it matches to such malicious software we can detect cyber attacks and can increase the computer security.

Mathematicians can identify topological invariant by representing the properties of geometrical spaces as a graph and also study their isomorphism properties.

2.0 Proposed Algorithm:Is_Isomorphic_Graph(**M1, L1, M2, L2**)**Input:**

M1 and M2 are the two given matrices (adjacency) of two graphs, with L1 and L2 number of nodes, respectively.

Output:

In this algorithm, using a heuristic approach, the isomorphism between the two graphs (of M1 and M2, respectively) will be checked and will give the output as-

- i. **1** - the graphs are **isomorphic**,
- ii. **0** - the graphs are **not isomorphic**,
- iii. **(-1)** - it is **not sure** that the graphs are isomorphic or not.

Steps:

1. IF **L1 not equals to L2** THEN, RETURN 0
2. IF **number of edges** of M1 and M2 are **not equal** THEN, RETURN 0
3. $N \leftarrow L2$
4. **Embed the node labels** in both M1 and M2, as first row and column.
5. **Embed the degrees** for all vertices, respectively, in M1 and M2, as last row and column.
6. **Both M1 and M2** will be sorted (non-decreasing manner) with respect to the degree sequence of the vertices.
7. Check **one-to-one correspondence** $\forall d_i \in d_{M1}$ (set of degrees in M1) **onto** $\forall d_j \in d_{M2}$ (set of degrees in M2).
IF condition **not satisfies** THEN, RETURN 0.
8. **Create an array Q** whose d^{th} $[0 \leq d \leq \{d_h / d_H\}]$, d_h / d_H denotes the highest degree present in M2] index will contain the lower index from where the vertex with degree d is starting in M2.
9. **Calculate a T** as $T \leftarrow \log \{(N - 1) / 2\}$
10. **REPEAT FOR** all $n \in \{1 \text{ to } N^T\}$, from **step 10 to step 14**
11. **Generate a random degree Dr** ($0 \leq Dr \leq d_h / d_H$).
12. **Select two random vertices**,
r1 and r2 (of degree Dr)
where, $r1 \neq r2$, and $Dr_L \leq (r1, r2) \leq Dr_U$
[Dr_L can be obtained as $Dr_L = Q_{Dr}$ and
 Dr_U can be computed as $Dr_U = \{Q_{(Dr+1)} - 1\}$]
13. Now, swap the rows of r1 and r2 and as well as the columns of r1 and r2.
14. **IF** M1 equals to M2 THEN, RETURN 1
15. RETURN (-1)

3.0 Description of the algorithm

In this algorithm, we have a special represent of graphs.

Following is an adjacency matrix representing a graph normally-

0	1	2	...	N-1	← Index

But, our representation is as follows-

-	0	1	2	...	N	N+1	← Index
0	-	1	2	3	...	N	← Node's Label
1	1						d1
2	2						d2
:	3						d3
.	:						:
N	N						dx
N+1	-	d1	d2	d3	...	dx	← Degree of respective Node

Let, M1 and M2 are as follows-

-	1	2	3	...	N	-
1						d1
2						d2
3						d3
:						:
N						dx
-	d1	d2	d3	...	dx	-

-	a	b	c	...	N	-
a						da
b						db
c						dc
:						:
N						dy
-	da	db	dc	...	dy	-

There after, M1 and M2 will be sorted with respect to the degree sequence (non-decreasing) of the vertices.

-	V1	V2	V3	...	Vx	-
V1						0
V2						:
V3						1
:						:
Vx						d_h
-	0	...	1	...	d_h	-

-	Va	Vb	Vc	...	Vy	-
Va						0
Vb						:
Vc						1
:						:
Vy						d_H
-	0	...	1	...	d_H	-

After performing the **sort operation**, M1 and M2 is rearranged so here, again we have to verify the **one-to-one and onto correspondence (bijection)** between M1 and M2. If there has no bijection then, we can say there has no isomorphism between Grp1 and Grp2.

And here, $d_h = d_H$.

Then, **create an array, Q =**

0	1	2	...	d_h / d_H
1

whose **0th index will contain the lower bound or initial index from where the vertex with degree 0 is starting in M2** and certainly 1st index will also contain the lower index from where the vertex with degree 1 is starting in M2.

Let, d^{th} ($0 \leq d \leq d_h / d_H$) index will contain the lower bound or initial index from where the vertex with degree d is starting in M2.

After that, perform the following steps-

Step 1:

generate a random degree, D_r ($0 \leq D_r \leq d_h / d_H$).

Step 2:

select two random vertices, r_1 and r_2 (of degree D_r) where, $r_1 \neq r_2$, and $D_{rL} \leq (r_1, r_2) \leq D_{rU}$

$$[D_{rL} = Q_{D_r} \text{ and } D_{rU} = \{ Q_{(D_r + 1)} - 1 \}]$$

Step 3:

swap the rows and columns of r_1 and r_2 vertices.

Step 4:

IF **M1 is equal to M2** then, TERMINATE as M1 and M2 are isomorphic
ELSE, for FALSE, Goto Step 1

Now, what is about the time complexity of the iteration?

With the heuristic approach, **the iteration** is bounded **within a polynomial time** which will be in form of N^T .

$N, N^2, \dots, N^T, \dots, N!$

Here, a **load factor** (LF) is introduced to calculate T.

$\therefore \mathbf{LF = (E / N)}$, where, E is the number of edges and N is the number of nodes in a graph. T will depend on LF or T will be a function of LF and $\mathbf{T \propto \text{DENSITY}}$ of graph.

Load factor (LF) will vary for variant type of graphs. Here, differentiating the graphs as the following types-

1. **Sparse**
2. **Dense**

Sparse

Dense

As the density of a sparse graph is less (with respect to dense graph), the value LF for this scenario will be lesser.

And for the dense graph LF will be higher (with respect to sparse graph). So, LF will depend on the density of a graph and the iteration is depend on LF.

For a sparse graph, $E = (N - 1)$

$$\therefore \mathbf{LF = \{ (N - 1) / N \} \text{ [ceiling]} \approx 1}$$

And **for a dense graph**, $E = \{ N * (N - 1) / 2 \}$

$$\therefore \mathbf{LF = [\{ N * (N - 1) / 2 \} / N]}$$

$$= \{ (N - 1) / 2 \} \text{ [ceiling]}$$

Here, $\mathbf{1 \leq LF \leq \{ (N - 1) / 2 \}}$

Now, **T will be a function of LF.**

Let, it will be the function of log...

Say,

$$\mathbf{T = \log LF \text{ [ceiling]}}$$

$$= \log \{ (N - 1) / 2 \}$$

Therefore,

$$N^T = N^{\log \{ (N - 1) / 2 \}}$$

Thus, we bound the complexity in quasi-polynomial time.

And additionally, to check the equality between M1 and M2, it will take N^2 time.

Over all,

$$O(N^T \times N^2)$$

$$= O(N^{\log \{ (N - 1) / 2 \}} \times N^2)$$

$$= O(N^{\log \{ \{ (N - 1) / 2 \} + 2 \}})$$

4.0 Reliability of the Algorithm: From the outputs of the algorithm, it could be stated that-

4.1 Given two graphs are isomorphic:

When, within the quasi-polynomial time, we can find out a permutation of Grp2 same as Grp1.

4.2 Given two graphs are not isomorphic:

This point can be ensured by that in both the graphs have unequal

- (a) Number of the nodes,
- (b) Number of the edges,
- (c) Degree sequence

4.3 Can't to say that given two graphs are isomorphic or not:

After all the checking and quasi-polynomial time iteration, we could unable to find the same match of Grp1 as Grp2.

5.0 Future Scope

1. In this heuristic approach, after selecting two we **have to find out two nodes randomly**. So, the **selection of the nodes should** be done that the selection of the nodes would **be really a random selection**.
2. As we are **using a heuristic algorithm** so, the algorithm should be **tested with a graph with the large number of nodes**.
3. Here, we assumed the **T as log (of base 2)**. Now, we have find out such a function which would be a better than the existing one that also would be a deterministic polynomial function.

6.0 Conclusion

In the current situation, we are unable to find out such a solution that solve the graph isomorphism problem with in a polynomial time complexity though, we try then, we need $N!$ comparisons which is not feasible to achieve for a large N .

Till now there are verity type of heuristic approaches to solve the problem but, no one can't be to choose the nodes such a manner that we could be efficient one. But, in our approach, we have tried to select the

graph randomly that should really so random and by selecting the random nodes, we can perceive for the nodes with the hope that the next selection could be the result.

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